

Charging and discharging tests of a composite of CaCl₂ and vermiculite for thermochemical adsorption energy storage

L. Vallese^{1,2,*}, G. Lombardo^{1,2}, D. Menegazzo^{1,2}, S. Bordignon², M. De Carli², S. Barison³, F. Agresti³, E. Baccega⁴, S. Bobbo¹, L. Fedele¹, M. Bottarelli⁴

¹ Construction Technologies Institute, National Research Council (CNR), Corso Stati Uniti 4, 35127 Padova, Italy

² Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Padova, Via Venezia 1, 35131, Padova, Italy

³ Institute of Condensed Matter Chemistry and Energy Technologies, National Research Council (CNR), Corso Stati Uniti 4, 35127 Padova, Italy

⁴ Department of Architecture, University of Ferrara, Via Quartieri 8, 44121, Ferrara, Italy

*Corresponding Author: laura.vallese@phd.unipd.it

Thermal Energy Storage plays a crucial role in increasing the flexibility of energy systems and facilitating the integration of renewable energy sources, particularly in the building sector. Salt hydrates combined in composite materials are the most suitable medium for thermochemical adsorption energy storage. This promising technology is characterised by higher energy density compared to sensible and latent heat energy storage systems.

In this work, the charging and discharging behaviour of a composite material consisting of vermiculite and CaCl₂ is evaluated through experimental tests. The aim is to obtain relevant results for the design of an innovative thermal energy storage prototype in the context of the European project ECHO.

A thermogravimetric evaluation was performed through employment of a thermobalance. The instrument measured the mass of water adsorbed and released by the material during the different phases, and possible deliquescence problems could be detected.

The discharging and charging cycles were investigated using a small lab-scale setup. The hydration of the composite occurred in a closed-loop system, while the circuit was opened during dehydration. The assessed air temperature lift between inlet and outlet of the material allowed the quantification of the power released in the discharging process.

The findings of this research provide useful information regarding the thermal performance and efficiency of the vermiculite-CaCl₂ composite as a candidate for thermochemical adsorption energy storage, thus contributing to the development and spread of these systems.

Keywords: Thermal energy storage, thermochemical material, salt hydrate

INTRODUCTION

Compared to the other TES technologies, thermochemical storage has higher energy storage density. Salt hydrates within composite materials are the most suitable TCMs for low temperature applications, thanks to their high energy densities and low temperatures required for dehydration [1].

This study experimentally assessed the required temperature for the dehydration of a vermiculite-CaCl₂ composite and the maximum achievable power during discharging.

METHODS

A composite of 83% of the salt hydrate CaCl₂ and 17% vermiculite was synthesised through the vacuum impregnation method. The first series of data was collected with a thermobalance. Firstly, the SIM was completely dehydrated at 160 °C in the oven. Secondly, the hydration of 7 g of SIM was performed at room temperature. The SIM sample was then dehydrated at 20 °C in the thermobalance. Hydration and dehydration tests

were repeated 5 times, increasing the dehydration temperature from 20 °C to 100 °C. The tests were then repeated with a new sample, considering only 85 °C and 95 °C for dehydration. The second part of the tests was performed in a circuit made of stainless steel tubes (100 mm diameter), including an electric heater and a fan (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Set-up for the charging and discharging cycles

120 g of SIM were placed in a section of the vertical tube in the left-hand side of Fig. 1, forming

a 50 mm thick bed. An ultrasonic humidifier was connected to the circuit during the discharging phase. The sensors included six T-type thermocouples (± 0.5 K), two sensors for temperature (NTC, ± 0.2 K) and relative humidity (capacitive, $\pm 2\%$), and a hot wire anemometer ($\pm 2\%$).

RESULTS

Fig. 2 shows the results for 2 discharging tests with the thermobalance. Between 40 °C and 60 °C, only two H₂O molecules are extracted from the TCM. At 80-85 °C, two further molecules are extracted. Dehydrating at temperatures between 90 °C and 100 °C leaves only one water molecule in the TCM. Only by dehydrating the TCM at 160 °C in the oven, the anhydrous state is reached.

Fig. 2 Mass ratio of adsorbed water and CaCl₂ at different temperatures (first test in red, second test in green).

During the tests with the circuit in Fig. 1, the maximum reached air temperature difference was 11.5 K (Fig. 3), with air velocity equal to 0.15 m/s. Therefore, the maximum power achievable is 130 W/kg_{TCM} (Eq. 1).

$$\dot{q}_{TCM}^{\max} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{air}} \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T}{m_{TCM}} \quad (1)$$

Since 80 g of water were adsorbed in 2 hours, the rate of adsorption is 333 g_w/(h·kg_{TCM}). The discharging in the same circuit was performed at 85 °C, reaching a RH of 3.5%.

CONCLUSIONS

A composite of vermiculite and CaCl₂ was tested during charging and discharging. 85 °C, which is the maximum supply temperature of the HP in the ECHO project, will not be sufficient for complete

dehydration of the material at room RH (40%). However, decreasing the RH, as in the circuit considered in the project, will allow to further improve the dehydration process. Hydration tests in the circuit showed a maximum achievable power of 130 W/kg_{TCM}. Future work will consist of further tests on an improved circuit, to confirm the obtained results.

Fig. 3 Discharging phase of the TCM.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme within the ECHO project, under grant agreement No. 101096368.

NOMENCLATURE

HP - Heat Pump;

SIM - Salt In Matrix;

TES - Thermal Energy Storage;

TCM - Thermochemical Material;

RH - Relative Humidity [%];

\dot{q}_{TCM}^{\max} - maximum power achievable per kg of TCM [W/kg_{TCM}];

\dot{m}_{air} - air mass flow rate [kg/s];

c_p - air specific heat [J/(kg·K)];

ΔT - air temperature difference between outlet and inlet [K];

m_{TCM} - mass of the TCM bed [kg].

Subscripts

W - water.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.-J. Clark, A. Mehrabadi, e M. Farid, «State of the art on salt hydrate thermochemical energy storage systems for use in building applications», *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 27, p. 101145, feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2019.101145.